

Explaining teachers' judgement accuracy of students' subjective well-being by students' individual characteristics and the teacher-student relationship

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates whether individual student characteristics and the teacher-student relationship can explain teachers' judgment (in)accuracy of three aspects of students' subjective well-being in early primary education. To this end, we analyse the consistency and specificity of teacher reports and self-reports ($N = 1582$) of Grade 3 students' subjective well-being by employing a multiple-indicator correlated trait-correlated method minus one model, with explanatory variables assessed in Grades 1 and 3. Our findings indicate that the consistency of teacher reports with students' self-reports is relatively low to moderate. Students' gender, academic achievement, intelligence and behavioural skills are significantly associated with the specificity of teacher reports of students' subjective well-being. The teacher-student relationship explains the specificity in teacher reports, with negative associations for conflicts and positive associations for closeness. This study highlights the relevance of behavioural skills and the teacher-student relationship for the alignment between teachers' judgment and self-reports of students' subjective well-being.

Educational relevance and implications statement: Accurate teacher judgment of students' subjective well-being is essential for addressing individual differences and for adaptive teaching, which in turn promotes students' academic and socio-emotional development. The findings of this study reveal that teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being in Grade 3 is only low to moderate. Students' gender, academic achievement, intelligence and behavioural skills assessed in Grades 1 and 3 significantly relate to teachers' judgment (in-)accuracy of students' subjective well-being. Furthermore, a conflicting teacher-student relationship is negatively associated with teachers' judgment accuracy, while closeness is positively associated. As one of the first studies, our findings point to a nuanced role of student behaviours and teacher-student relationships in shaping teachers' judgments of students' subjective well-being.

1. Introduction

Students' subjective well-being has gained prominence in both research and educational practice. The rapidly growing literature indicates that it is regarded as a key factor influencing learning and as a valuable educational outcome in its own right (e.g., Kanonire et al., 2020; Morinaj & Hascher, 2022; Steinmayr et al., 2018), particularly relevant in the early primary school years, as it can set the stage for positive development in school (e.g., Cefai & Camilleri, 2014; Dempsey et al., 2024). Simultaneously, students' subjective well-being serves as a

key indicator for inclusive education (e.g., Goldan et al., 2022; Wächter et al., 2024) and adaptive teaching, as it affects teachers' decisions on how to design classroom interventions and instruction (Kolovou et al., 2024; Praetorius et al., 2015), which is especially important given the increasing diversity of students (Ohle & McElvany, 2015). Still, making judgments about this internal construct appears to be challenging (Urhahne & Zhu, 2015). Previous studies have shown that teachers' judgment accuracy regarding different aspects of students' subjective well-being is only low to moderate compared to their accuracy in judging other student characteristics (Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021).

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Factors explaining the (in-)accuracy of teacher judgments of students' subjective well-being has rarely been examined, and most studies have relied on cross-sectional designs (Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021). Research in the field of inclusive education indicates that teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being is associated with students' gender, academic achievement, special needs and first language (Schwab et al., 2020; Südkamp et al., 2018; Venetz et al., 2019; Zurbriggen et al., 2023). According to Kaiser et al. (2013), students' behavioural engagement also shapes teachers' judgments of students' achievement. In line with Funder's (1995, 2012) realistic accuracy model, it can be assumed that teachers infer their judgments based on behavioural cues available when assessing a student's subjective well-being. Still, studies on teacher judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being that consider students' behaviour are scarce.

In addition to individual characteristics, teachers' involvement in their relationships with students is likely to play a significant role in aligning teachers' and students' perspectives on social characteristics (Hoffman et al., 2015; Marucci et al., 2018). Close and low-conflict teacher-student relationships contribute to an environment conducive to successful learning and well-being (Bakchich et al., 2023; Koomen & Jellesma, 2015; Saxer et al., 2024). A recent study by Saxer et al. (2024) indicates that the association between the teacher-student relationship and students' subjective well-being varies depending on the well-being dimensions considered, as well as gender and at-risk family context (i.e., migration background, low socio-economic status). A positive teacher-student relationship proves particularly salient during the early years of school (e.g., Ansari et al., 2020; McGrath & van Bergen, 2015; Verschuere & Koomen, 2012). It can be assumed that teachers who know students for a longer period are better able to judge their subjective well-being. Notwithstanding this seemingly logical assumption, the study by Praetorius et al. (2015) revealed that teacher judgment accuracy of students' academic self-concept – as one aspect of school-related well-being – in classroom settings does not significantly differ from judgment accuracy in a zero-acquaintance situation.

Thus, this study aims to examine teachers' judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being in early primary education and to investigate whether individual characteristics – particularly students' behaviour – and the teacher-student relationship can explain (in)accuracy in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being.

1.1. Conceptualising students' subjective well-being in school

While educational research generally agrees on the importance of students' subjective well-being for their learning processes and achievement in school (e.g., Amholt et al., 2020; Bückler et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2024), its theoretical understanding and assessment remain diverse. Often used interchangeably with terms such as happiness or mental health, subjective well-being is considered a broad, multidimensional construct (Schimmack, 2008). A common agreement is that subjective well-being captures individuals' perceptions and consists of both an affective and a cognitive component (Busseri & Sadava, 2011). This consensus is based on the widely acknowledged conception by Diener (1984), which defines subjective well-being as the reflective cognitive judgments individuals make about their lives in general or in specific life domains (e.g., work, school, family), as well as their positive and negative emotional responses to ongoing life experiences or specific situations (Diener et al., 2018).

Applied to the school context, the *affective component* of subjective well-being reflects positive feelings, emotions or affective attitudes towards school, while the *cognitive component* refers to cognitive self-evaluation or satisfaction in terms of academic competencies. The latter component corresponds with students' *academic self-concept*, one of the most important constructs in educational and motivational research (e.g., Marsh et al., 2015; Marsh & Martin, 2011; Retelsdorf et al., 2014). Additionally, several researchers have suggested including *social aspects* as an important component of children's subjective well-

being in school (e.g., Hascher, 2008; Kytälä et al., 2023; Tobia et al., 2019). This proposal is reflected in Hascher's (2010) prominent conception, where students' subjective well-being is defined as a multidimensional construct encompassing positive attitudes towards school, enjoyment in school, the absence of worries about school, a positive academic self-concept and the absence of social problems as well as physical complaints in school. In our study, we follow this comprehensive, multi-dimensional conception of school-related subjective well-being, by considering one affective aspect (i.e., emotional well-being at school), one cognitive aspect (i.e., academic self-concept) and one social aspect (i.e., social inclusion in class).

1.2. Teacher assessment of students' subjective well-being

Subjective well-being is, by definition, a construct that relies on self-report measures (Lucas, 2018). Gathering self-reports can be challenging when studying the subjective well-being of younger students (Dempsey et al., 2024), due to difficulties in language comprehension and reading, or in differentiating between similar constructs (Marsh et al., 2005).

As already mentioned, teachers' judgment accuracy regarding different aspects of students' subjective well-being is known to be only low to moderate compared to other student characteristics (Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021). It is important to acknowledge that students' subjective well-being, as such is not visible and thus cannot be directly observed by others (e.g., teachers, parents), but rather inferred from observable cues. According to the meta-analysis by Kenny and West (2010), greater visibility of a construct is significantly associated with higher self-other agreement.

The affective component of students' subjective well-being is particularly difficult to detect. Accordingly, studies have shown low teacher judgment accuracy for *emotional aspects* of students' well-being at school, such as their enjoyment at school, worries about school (Urhahne & Zhu, 2015) or emotional inclusion (Venetz et al., 2019). In contrast, most studies report moderate accuracy in teachers' judgments of students' *academic self-concept* (e.g., Pielmeier et al., 2018; Praetorius et al., 2013; Urhahne et al., 2011). This higher accuracy can partly be explained by the better visibility of corresponding cues; for instance, information about students' achievement can enhance teachers' judgment accuracy of students' academic self-concept (Helm et al., 2018).

Evidence on teachers' judgment accuracy of *social aspects* is inconclusive. Several studies have shown low teacher judgment accuracy for social inclusion in class (Schwab et al., 2020; Venetz et al., 2019; Zurbriggen et al., 2023) or other social aspects (Urhahne & Zhu, 2015), while Gomez (2014) found moderate to high accuracy for prosocial behaviour and peer problems, respectively. In most other studies, teacher judgments were compared with peer reports (e.g., Kwon et al., 2012; Südkamp et al., 2018). The findings by Wilbert et al. (2020) underscore the importance of differentiating between peer-reported and self-reported social characteristics: While teachers were moderately accurate in identifying social acceptance and rejection by peers, their accuracy was notably lower when assessing students' self-perceived social inclusion in class.

1.3. Models on teachers' judgment accuracy

In educational research, most theoretical models proposed to explain teachers' judgment accuracy focus on students' academic achievement or achievement-related characteristics (e.g., Südkamp et al., 2012). The *two-part conceptual model on teachers' assessment competence* by Herppich et al. (2018; cf. also Südkamp & Praetorius, 2017) provides an extended framework of previous models, by incorporating various research approaches dealing with teachers' assessment from different angles (e.g., assessment products, processes, practices). Although the model focuses on teachers' assessment competence of 'quantifiable performance,' the process part of the model illustrates the complexity of the judgment process, which entails collecting, selecting, analysing, interpreting and

integrating information to gain a reliable and valid judgment of a student's characteristics. The structural model part highlights that the nature of the assessment depends on the specific context or assessment situation. Compared to the assessment of academic achievement, judging students' subjective well-being is a more ubiquitous, mostly unconscious activity embedded in everyday teaching. Moreover, while the evaluation of teacher judgment accuracy of academic achievement is based on quantifiable performance measures, one peculiarity of judgment accuracy regarding subjective well-being is that self-reports serve as the reference (Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021). In this vein, judgment accuracy of subjective well-being is defined as self-other agreement.

A particularly suitable model to explain self-other agreement – and thus teachers' judgment accuracy of subjective well-being – originates from personality psychology: Funder's *realistic accuracy model* (Funder, 1995, 2012). This widely accepted model illustrates how accurate judgments of personality traits – defined as 'patterns of thought, emotion, and behaviour' (Funder, 2012, p. 177) – are formed and identifies four key conditions under which accurate judgments are most likely to occur: relevance, availability, detection and utilisation. To put it simply, the model postulates that relevant behavioural information must be available (e.g., specific student behaviour) and detected by a judge (e.g., a teacher), then utilised properly to reach an accurate judgment. Thus, if behavioural cues are either unavailable or not utilised correctly, teachers' evaluations are unlikely to yield accurate judgments. Consequently, as previously noted, the visibility of traits through behavioural cues is a strong predictor of judgment accuracy or self-other agreement (Kenny & West, 2010).

In research on judgment accuracy regarding behavioural and social characteristics, teacher-student agreement has sometimes been referred to as *teacher attunement* (e.g., Ahn & Rodkin, 2014; Hamm et al., 2011; Hoffman et al., 2015; Marucci et al., 2018). According to Ahn and Rodkin (2014), teacher attunement corresponds to a teacher's knowledge of self-perceived social characteristics of their students, which includes not only characteristics at the individual level (e.g., problem behaviour, peer nominations) but also at the classroom level (e.g., social networks, social dynamics in the classroom). Teacher attunement is typically operationalised as the extent to which teacher reports of students' social characteristics overlap or align with the reports of their students (Marucci et al., 2021).

1.4. Factors explaining teachers' judgment accuracy

1.4.1. Individual student characteristics

Students' gender has been shown to affect teachers' judgments regarding students' subjective well-being. Schwab et al. (2020) found small positive effects of gender on teacher ratings of students' emotional well-being and social inclusion, indicating that teachers overestimated emotional and social aspects of girls' subjective well-being compared to those of boys. In the study by Venetz et al. (2019), such a gender effect was shown only for the academic self-concept, while Zurbriggen et al. (2023) found gender effects on teachers' judgment accuracy of all three aforementioned aspects. Urhahne and Zhu (2015) reported gender differences in teacher ratings for students' attitudes towards school, worries and physical complaints, but the interaction term was only significant for physical complaints.

Urhahne and Zhu (2015) also accounted for students' academic achievement level as a potential moderator of teacher judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being. Their findings revealed that teachers reported larger differences for high versus low achievers regarding affective aspects of subjective well-being, whereas no significant differences were found for social problems, academic self-concept and physical complaints. In the study by Zurbriggen et al. (2023), students' academic achievement was found to have the strongest effect of the characteristics included on teacher judgments of emotional well-being, social inclusion and academic self-concept, with higher academic achievement associated with more positive teacher ratings of

subjective well-being compared to self-reports.

Since teacher ratings of students' cognitive abilities are highly correlated with academic achievement (Machts et al., 2016), it can be assumed that students' intelligence (i.e., general cognitive abilities) also affects teachers' judgments of students' subjective well-being. According to Machts et al. (2016), cognitive abilities are evaluated (implicitly) by teachers on a daily basis, influencing how teachers create adequate learning environments for students in their class. Thus, teacher judgments of students' intelligence play an important role in adaptive teaching (Fischbach et al., 2013).

Evidence further suggests that teacher judgments are biased against *minority or marginalised groups*, such as students from ethnic minorities or those with low socio-economic status (e.g., Glock et al., 2015; Meissel et al., 2017). However, biases towards minority groups have rarely been examined concerning teachers' judgments of students' subjective well-being. For students' first language (as an indicator of migration background), it was found that teachers underestimate the academic self-concept of students who speak German (the teaching language) as a second language (Zurbriggen et al., 2023).

Despite its theoretically assumed relevance, students' behaviour has seldom been the focus as a predictor of teacher judgment accuracy of subjective well-being. According to findings of Kaiser et al. (2013), students' behavioural engagement affects teachers' judgments of students' academic achievement. In terms of *problem behaviour*, Liu et al. (2004) found lower agreement between teacher reports and self-reports of threatening behaviour for students with higher levels of aggression and peer rejection. Similarly, a study by Neal et al. (2011) indicates that students' aggressive behaviour can result in lower teacher-student agreement regarding classroom social networks. In contrast, Pearl et al. (2007) reported higher teacher judgment accuracy regarding social network participation for students with behavioural problems. Wilbert et al. (2020) did not find an effect of students' behaviour problems on teacher rating accuracy of students' social inclusion. Studies considering *prosocial behaviour* suggest that teachers are more attuned to students' positive than negative behaviour. Findings by Marucci et al. (2018) demonstrated that judgment accuracy (i.e., attunement) was higher for prosocial behaviour than for risk behaviour, possibly because students tend to hide risk behaviour from teachers, whereas prosocial behaviour is likely to be displayed more openly.

1.4.2. Quality and length of the teacher-student relationship

Several studies have emphasised the importance of a good teacher-student relationship for students' well-being in school (review by McGrath & Van Bergen, 2015). The recent study by Saxer et al. (2024) showed that closeness in the teacher-student relationship was positively related to positive emotional aspects of subjective well-being and to the academic self-concept, while conflicts were significantly negatively related to the same aspects of subjective well-being. For the academic self-concept, similar findings were reported by McFarland et al. (2016). Furthermore, there is evidence that the quality of the teacher-student relationship plays an important role in students' peer relationships in class (Endedijk et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, to our knowledge, the teacher-student relationship has been neglected as a potential predictor in research on teacher judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being. This is surprising, as a positive relationship could encourage students to share their emotions and experiences more openly, providing teachers with better insights. Similarly, teachers who are attuned to students' well-being cues may foster stronger relationships. This aligns Hamm et al.'s (2011) concept of teacher attunement, which they define as an aspect of teachers' involvement with their students and their awareness of social dynamics in the classroom.

Studies investigating teacher attunement regarding social characteristics indicate that the length of the relationship might affect the accuracy of teacher reports. For instance, Marucci et al. (2018) found a positive association between teacher attunement regarding peer

nominations and the amount of time teachers spent with their students. The findings by Harks and Hannover (2017) demonstrated that the more lessons teachers taught per class, the better they were able to judge sympathy-based peer interactions of their students in the classroom. Furthermore, teachers in elementary schools were better attuned to their students' sympathy-based peer interactions than secondary school teachers.

1.5. The present study

The first aim of the present study was to examine teachers' judgment accuracy of three aspects of students' subjective well-being (i.e., emotional well-being, social inclusion, academic self-concept) in their first years of primary education. Based on theoretical considerations and previous studies (e.g., Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021; Venetz et al., 2019), we hypothesised that teachers' judgment accuracy would be low for emotional well-being (Hypothesis 1a) and social inclusion (Hypothesis 1b) and moderate for academic self-concept (Hypothesis 1c).

Second, we investigated whether teachers' judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being could be explained by students' individual characteristics. Based on theoretical considerations and past research (e.g., Schwab et al., 2020; Urhahne & Zhu, 2015; Venetz et al., 2019; Zurbruggen et al., 2023), we assumed that teachers rate girls' subjective well-being more positively than that of boys (Hypothesis 2a), and more negatively for students from at-risk family contexts than for other students (Hypothesis 2b), each compared to the self-reports. Past findings (Urhahne & Zhu, 2015; Zurbruggen et al., 2023) led us to further expect that academic achievement would positively affect teacher judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 2c). Similarly, a positive effect was expected for students' intelligence (Hypothesis 2d). Based on Funder (2012) and research on teacher attunement (e.g., Marucci et al., 2018; Neal et al., 2011), we assumed that students' behavioural problems negatively affect teacher judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 2e), while students' prosocial behaviour positively affects judgment accuracy (Hypothesis 2f).

Third, we examined whether the quality of the teacher-student relationship could explain teachers' judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being. Based on theoretical considerations and empirical evidence, we assumed that closeness would be positively associated with teacher judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 3a), while a negative association for conflicting relationships was expected (Hypothesis 3b). Finally, we investigated in an exploratory manner whether the duration of a teacher-student relationship affects teacher judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being.

2. Methods

2.1. Sample and procedure

The current study is based on data from the ZEPPELIN (Zurich Equity Prevention Project with Parents Participation and Integration) longitudinal study, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). More specifically, we draw on data from the two measurement occasions t7 and t9 of the follow-up studies ZEPPELIN 5-8 (SNSF Grant Number: 10FI14_170408) and ZEPPELIN 9-13 (SNSF Grant Number: 10FI14_198055). At t7, children were in Grade 1 of primary education. At t9, they were in Grade 3. In the present study, t7 corresponds to T1, and t9 to T2.

In concordance with the Declaration of Helsinki all parents gave informed consent separately for T1 and T2 for the participation of their children in the study. Separate approval for compliance with data protection regulations and access to schools were obtained from the city of Zurich. School deans and teachers supported participation in their schools. The Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich (Switzerland)

approved the ZEPPELIN study protocol (KEK-ZH 2013-0278; BASEC-2020-00154).

The schools in this study were primarily located in the Swiss canton of Zurich. Compulsory education begins with two years of pre-primary education, followed by six years of primary school starting at age six. The class reassignments vary by school; while some reallocate students after kindergarten, second grade, and fourth grade, others do so after kindergarten and third grade. Students spend in first grade 24 lessons per week and in third grade 27 per week in school. These lessons are mostly taught by the homeroom teachers.

Data collection took place in class and was conducted by trained student assistants. The assessments (e.g., performance tests, student questionnaires) were split over two school days. Homeroom teachers were also given a questionnaire to assess the teacher-student relationship and the subjective well-being of selected students in their class (approximately 5 students per class). The students were selected manually by the student assistants based on predefined criteria to ensure a balanced sample in terms of gender and first language (German vs. other language).

A total of 125 classes, comprising 2375 students, were invited to participate in the study. Of these, 120 classes agreed to take part. The average class size was 19 students, of which an average of 14 per class participating (i.e., with parental informed consent). This resulted in a sample of 1582 grade 3 students (51.6 % girls), with an average age of 9.5 years ($SD = 0.48$) at T2. For 59.8 % of the students, German – the teaching language – was also their primary language (i.e., they always or usually spoke in German at home). Additionally, 22.5 % of the students sometimes spoke German at home, while 17.6 % rarely or never did. 91.7 % ($n = 1160$) of the students remained in the same class from Grade 1 to Grade 3, and 73.3 % had the same homeroom teacher at T1 and T2. At T2, 107 homeroom teachers (89.1 % female) responded to the questionnaire, corresponding to a response rate of 89 %. On average, the teachers possessed 14.8 years of teaching experience ($SD = 12.1$ years).

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Students' subjective well-being

Students' subjective well-being was assessed in Grade 3 (T2) from both the student's and teacher's perspectives using the German version of the Perceptions of Inclusion Questionnaire (PIQ; Venetz et al., 2015). The PIQ consists of three scales: emotional well-being, social inclusion and academic self-concept, each measured with four items on a Likert-type scale with four categories (0 = *not at all true*, 1 = *rather not true*, 2 = *somewhat true*, 3 = *certainly true*). Several studies have shown that the student version (PIQ-S) yields good psychometric properties (e.g., DeVries et al., 2018; Knickenberg et al., 2022; Zdoupas & Laubenstein, 2022; Zurbruggen et al., 2019). For the teacher version (PIQ-T), the factorial validity and internal consistency of the three scales also proved to be good (Schwab et al., 2020; Venetz et al., 2019).

2.2.2. Students' gender

Gender was assessed using information from the parents (1 = female, 0 = male).

2.2.3. Students from at-risk subsample

The criteria for an at-risk family context were met when parents exhibited at least two distinct risk factors in the following domains: material (e.g., cramped living conditions), social (e.g., lack of social support), family (e.g., single parenthood) and personal (e.g., mental illness). The family's level of psychosocial risk was assessed with the Heidelberg Stress Scale (HBS; Sidor et al., 2012) around the time of the children's birth (for further information: Neuhauser et al., 2015).

2.2.4. Students' intelligence

Students' intelligence was measured using the German short version of the Culture Fair Intelligence Test for children (CFT 1-R; Weiß &

Osterland, 2013) at T1. The test measures figural perception under time pressure and figural thinking. The overall performance reflects nonverbal cognitive ability.

2.2.5. Students' academic achievement

Basic reading and mathematical skills were assessed at T1. Reading skills were evaluated using the test 'Würzburger Leiseleseprobe – Revision' (WLLP-R; Schneider et al., 2011), which measures decoding speed. Mathematical skills were assessed using a short version of the 'Test mathematischer Basiskompetenzen' (MBK-1+; Ennemoser et al., 2017). The test measures basic mathematical competencies (i.e., basic skills, simple and deep understanding of numbers). T-scores were used for both

academic achievement tests.

2.2.6. Students' behavioural skills

Students' behavioural skills were evaluated by the homeroom teachers at both T1 and T2 using the German version of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ; Goodman, 1997; Klasen et al., 2003). The SDQ encompasses four problem scales: conduct problems, hyperactivity, peer problems and emotional problems, as well as a scale for prosocial behaviour. Each scale consists of five items rated on three categories (0 = not true, 1 = somewhat true, 2 = certainly true). The reliability coefficients ranged from $\omega = 0.83$ (95 % CI = [0.80, 0.86]) to $\omega = 0.94$ (95 % CI = [0.93, 0.95]) at T1, and from $\omega = 0.85$ (95 % CI =

Fig. 1. (a) Simple multi-trait multi-method (MTMM) model; (b) correlated trait-correlated method minus one (CT-C[M-1]) model. EMO = emotional well-being, SOC = social inclusion, ASC = academic self-concept, S = self-report, T = teacher report. Y^*_{ijk} = observed indicator (i = item, j = trait, k = method); λ_{ijk} = factor loadings.

[0.83, 0.88]) to $\omega = 0.95$ (95 % CI = [0.94, 0.96]) at T2, indicating acceptable to good internal consistency for the SDQ scales.

2.2.7. Teacher-student relationship

Teachers assessed the teacher-student relationship at T1 and T2 using the short form of the Student Teacher Relationship Scale (STRS; Pianta, 2001). The closeness scale consists of eight items (e.g., 'I share an affectionate, warm relationship with this child'), and the conflict scale consists of seven items (e.g., 'This child and I always seem to be struggling with each other'). Each item is rated on a Likert-type scale with five categories (0 = *definitely does not apply*, 1 = *not really*, 2 = *neutral, not sure*, 3 = *applies somewhat*, 4 = *definitely applies*). The internal consistency of the closeness scale was $\omega = 0.90$ (95 % CI = [0.89, 0.91]) at both T1 and T2, and for the conflict scale, $\omega = 0.88$ (95 % CI = [0.86, 0.89]) at T1 and $\omega = 0.90$ (95 % CI = [0.88, 0.91]) at T2, indicating good internal consistency for both scales.

2.3. Analyses

As a preliminary analyses, we tested the factorial validity of the PIQ-S and PIQ-T using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The internal consistency of the scales was evaluated by McDonald's ω (McDonald, 1999), which has been shown to provide a more accurate estimate of internal consistency compared to other indices such as the coefficient alpha (Dunn et al., 2014). To evaluate the correlations between the scales of the two PIQ versions, we fitted a simple CFA multi-trait-multi-method (MTMM) model with a separate latent factor for each trait-method unit (TMU), allowing all TMU factors to correlate (Geiser et al., 2014; Marsh & Hocevar, 1988; cf. Fig. 1a).

The model fit was assessed using the χ^2 test, as well as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). CFI and TLI values >0.95 indicate a good fit to the data (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Marsh et al., 2004). RMSEA values <0.06 indicate a close fit to the data, while SRMR values below 0.08 represent a good fit.

To address our first research question, we specified a correlated trait-correlated method minus one [CT-C(M-1)] model (Eid, 2000; Eid et al., 2003). The CT-C(M-1) model corresponds to a CFA-MTMM approach suitable for studying the convergent validity of structurally different (i.e., not interchangeable) methods and for estimating 'pure' method effects (i.e., method specificity) that are unrelated to trait differences (for more information on the CT-C(M-1) model compared to other relevant models, see e.g., Eid et al., 2008; Eid et al., 2016; Geiser et al., 2012; Koch, Eid, & Lochner, 2018). In the CT-C(M-1) model, one method (or several methods) is contrasted with the reference method to assess the consistency of the two (or more) methods as well as the specificity of the non-reference method (i.e., method effect). As we focused on students' subjective well-being, the student's self-report was defined as the *reference method*, and the teacher report as the *non-reference method* (cf. Fig. 1b). While the *consistency* represents the part of the non-reference method that is shared with the reference method, the *specificity* corresponds to the part of a trait measured by a (non-reference) method that cannot be explained by the reference method (Eid et al., 2008; Koch, Eid, & Lochner, 2018).

To enhance the comprehensibility of the two concepts consistency and (method) specificity, we calculated also the *variance components* indicating the *degree* of consistency and method specificity in the CT-C(M-1) model (Eid et al., 2008; Koch, Eid, & Lochner, 2018). The variance coefficients for the aggregated CT-C(M-1) model were calculated using formulas provided in Appendix B by Eid et al. (2003). Aggregated means that all items belonging to the same TMU were included in the calculation of the variance components. The *consistency coefficient* is equivalent to the proportion of (observed) variance in teacher reports that is common with students' self-reports of, for instance, their emotional well-being, while the *specificity coefficient* presents the

proportion of variance in teacher reports that is not shared with the students' self-reports. Furthermore, we calculated the *latent correlations* by extracting the square root of the consistency coefficients (Eid et al., 2003) to ensure better comparability with the results of other studies on teacher judgment accuracy. According to Cohen's (2013) suggestions, and in line with the review on teacher judgment accuracy by Urhahne and Wijnia (2021), correlation coefficients between 0.10 and 0.30 can be interpreted as small, between 0.30 and 0.50 moderate, and above 0.50 as large effects.

To address the second research question, we related the hypothesised student characteristics as explanatory variables to the CT-C(M-1) model. More specifically, the trait factors of the reference method (i.e., student self-reports) and the trait-specific method factors of the non-reference method (i.e., teacher reports) were regressed on the following explanatory variables: the two dichotomous variables, students' gender (male vs. female) and psychosocial at-risk family context (not at-risk vs. at-risk), as well as the three continuous variables, students' intelligence, reading comprehension and mathematics achievement. Next, the five SDQ scales, both at T1 and T2 (each treated using a separate model), were added as manifest variables. For the behavioural skills (SDQ scales) that were rated by teachers at T1, only the subsample of students with the same homeroom teacher at T1 and T2 was used.

To address to third research question, we entered the two scales, closeness and conflict (in the teacher-student relationship), at T1 and T2 as manifest explanatory variables to the factors in the CT-C(M-1) model (again each treated using a separate model). Again, the characteristics that were rated by teachers at T1, only the subsample of students with the same homeroom teacher at T1 and T2 was used. The standardized regression coefficients of the explanatory variables on the trait-specific method effects in the CT-C(M-1) model can be interpreted as effect sizes akin to Cohen's *d*, with 0.20 as small, 0.50 as medium and 0.80 as large effect (Cohen, 2013; Ellis, 2010).

All analyses were conducted using Mplus Version 8.11 (Muthén & Muthén, 1998–2017). Parameters were estimated using the robust weighted least square means and variances (WLSMV) estimator, which is recommended for categorical variables and skewed distributions (Rhemtulla et al., 2012), and especially for CT-C(M-1) models (Nussbeck et al., 2006). Given the clustered data structure (i.e., students clustered in classrooms, teachers rated students in their classes), we used the design-based complex sample option implemented in Mplus to adjust standard errors according to the clustering. The intraclass correlation coefficients for the PIQ items ranged between 0.01 and 0.20 ($M = 0.06$). Examples of our model syntaxes are provided in the supplementary material. The data of this study are available from the last author, upon reasonable request.

3. Results

3.1. Factorial validity, reliability and correlations of the PIQ scales

As shown in Table 1, the fit indices for the three-factor CFA models indicated a good fit to the data for both the PIQ-S (Model 1) and the PIQ-T (Model 2). The reliability coefficients for the PIQ-S ranged from $\omega = 0.76$ (95 % CI = [0.74, 0.78]) to $\omega = 0.90$ (95 % CI = [0.89, 0.91]), and for the PIQ-T from $\omega = 0.92$ (95 % CI = [0.91, 0.93]) to $\omega = 0.96$ (95 % CI = [0.95, 0.97]), indicating good internal consistency of the scales (Table 2).

The simple CFA-MTMM model showed a good fit to the data (Table 1, Model 3). The monotrait-heteromethod correlation (Table 2, in bold type) was higher for academic self-concept than for social and emotional well-being. Overall, the heterotrait-monomethod correlations (Table 2, marked in dark grey) were higher for teacher reports than for student self-reports, indicating lower discriminant validity for teacher reports than for student self-reports.

Table 1
Summary of model fit indices.

Model	χ^2_{wlsmv}	df	p	CFI	TLI	RMSEA [90 % CI]	SRMR
(1) CFA Student	417.74	51	< 0.001	0.963	0.952	0.068 [0.062, 0.074]	0.050
(2) CFA Teacher	152.76	51	< 0.001	0.995	0.994	0.064 [0.052, 0.076]	0.032
(3) CFA MTMM	612.47	237	< 0.001	0.986	0.983	0.032 [0.029, 0.035]	0.047
(4) CT-C(M-1)	611.92	228	< 0.001	0.985	0.982	0.033 [0.030, 0.036]	0.046

Note. WLSMV = weighted least square mean and variance adjusted estimator; CFI = comparative fit index; TLI = Tucker–Lewis index; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; 90 % CI = 90 % confidence interval; SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual.

Table 2
Correlations, means, variances, reliabilities (McDonald ω) of the latent factors in the CFA MTMM model.

	Student self-report			Teacher report		
	EMO	SOC	ASC	EMO	SOC	ASC
<i>>Student</i>						
EMO	(0.90)					
SOC	0.41***	(0.76)				
ASC	0.38***	0.45***	(0.78)			
<i>Teacher</i>						
EMO	0.40***	0.25***	0.33***	(0.96)		
SOC	0.28***	0.40***	0.17***	0.60***	(0.92)	
ASC	0.10	0.22***	0.64***	0.52***	0.33***	(0.96)
M	1.83	1.84	1.73	2.40	1.87	1.39
Variance	0.74	0.34	0.58	0.86	0.71	0.86

Note. EMO = emotional well-being, SOC = social inclusion, ASC = academic self-concept. Main diagonal (values in parentheses): reliabilities (McDonald ω). Monotrait-heteromethod correlations are in bold type and marked in light grey; heterotrait-monomethod correlations are marked in dark grey.

*** $p < .001$.

3.2. Consistency and specificity

The CT-C(M-1) model fitted the data well (Table 1, Model 4). The correlations between the trait factors of the reference method were significant and ranged between 0.38 and 0.45 (Table 3). The moderate positive correlations of the (non-reference) method factors indicate that teacher ratings can be generalised to some extent across the three traits, and that the teacher ratings discriminated somewhat less between emotional well-being and academic self-concept ($r = 0.52$) and social inclusion ($r = 0.53$) than between social inclusion and academic self-concept ($r = 0.35$).

Four out of six correlations between the trait factors and the trait-

Table 3
Correlations of the trait and trait-specific method factors in the CT-C(M-1) model.

	Trait factors			Trait-specific method factors		
	EMO-S	SOC-S	ASC-S	EMO-T	SOC-T	ASC-T
<i>Trait factors</i>						
EMO-S	1.00					
SOC-S	0.41***	1.00				
ASC-S	0.38***	0.45***	1.00			
<i>Trait-specific method factors</i>						
EMO-T		0.10	0.20***	1.00		
SOC-T	0.13*		-0.02	0.53***	1.00	
ASC-T	-0.19***	-0.09		0.52***	0.35***	1.00

Note. Trait factors = true-score variable of the student self-reports (reference method); trait-specific method factors = method-specific deviations from the reference method for one trait, thus specific to teacher reports (non-reference method). S = student report, T = teacher report, EMO = emotional well-being, SOC = social inclusion, ASC = academic self-concept. Empty cells indicate non-admissible correlations that were fixed to 0.

* $p < .05$.

*** $p < .001$.

specific method factors were significant ($-0.19 \leq r \leq 0.20$). For instance, the small negative correlation between the method factor of academic self-concept and the trait factor of emotional well-being ($r = -0.19$) indicates that teachers tended to underestimate the academic self-concept of students with higher emotional well-being, and vice versa.

In Table 4, the estimated variance components for the observed and true-score variables of the aggregated CT-C(M-1) model are reported (see Table S1 in the supplementary material for the variance components of each item). The consistency coefficient of the true-score variables varied between 0.16 and 0.40, indicating that for instance only 16 % of the variance in teacher reports of students' emotional well-being was shared with their self-reports (Fig. 2). Thus, the consistency of teacher reports with student self-reports was relatively low for emotional well-being (Hypothesis 1a) and social inclusion (Hypothesis 1b) and higher for the academic self-concept (Hypothesis 1c). In turn, the specificity in teacher reports was relatively high, with the highest specificity for emotional well-being (0.84) and lowest for the academic self-concept (0.60). The latent correlations calculated based on the consistency coefficients show that the correlations between student self-reports and teacher reports were moderate for emotional well-being ($r = 0.40$) and social inclusion ($r = 0.42$) and relatively high ($r = 0.63$) for academic self-concept.

3.3. Students' individual characteristics as explanatory variables

The standardized regression coefficients of the student characteristics included as explanatory variables are reported in Table 5. These coefficients can be interpreted as effect sizes akin to Cohen's d . Students' gender had a significant, small positive effect on trait-specific method factors (i.e., specificity in teacher reports) for emotional well-being and social inclusion (Hypothesis 2a), but not for academic self-concept. An at-risk family context yielded small negative effects, but only on the trait

Table 4
Estimated variance components in the aggregated CT-C(M-1) model.

Rating	Observed variables		True-score variables		
	Consistency	Method specificity	Consistency	Method specificity	Latent correlation ^a
<i>Emotional well-being</i>					
Student			1.00		
Teacher	0.15	0.81	0.16	0.84	0.40
<i>Social inclusion</i>					
Student			1.00		
Teacher	0.17	0.76	0.18	0.82	0.42
<i>Academic self-concept</i>					
Student			1.00		
Teacher	0.38	0.57	0.40	0.60	0.63

Note. Aggregated: all items belonging to the same variable were included in the calculation of the variance components.

^a Latent correlation with the reference method ($\sqrt{\text{consistency}}$).

Fig. 2. Variance components consistency and specificity, based on the aggregated CT-C(M-1) model.

Table 5

Standardized regression coefficients and standard errors (in Parentheses) of the student characteristics as explanatory variables on trait and method factors.

	Trait factors			Trait-specific method factors		
	EMO-S	SOC-S	ASC-S	EMO-T	SOC-T	ASC-T
Gender (female)	0.289** (0.028)	0.047 (0.031)	-0.073* (0.031)	0.156** (0.054)	0.163** (0.057)	0.062 (0.067)
At-risk family context	-0.054* (0.026)	-0.081* (0.032)	-0.111*** (0.027)	-0.016 (0.038)	-0.005 (0.034)	-0.070 (0.046)
Reading achievement T1	0.064 (0.042)	0.165*** (0.036)	0.348*** (0.035)	0.209*** (0.066)	0.078* (0.065)	0.429*** (0.062)
Mathematics achievement T1	-0.033 (0.036)	0.203*** (0.029)	0.348*** (0.032)	0.144** (0.055)	0.039 (0.062)	0.358*** (0.046)
Intelligence T1	0.036 (0.036)	0.088* (0.043)	0.308*** (0.034)	0.209*** (0.064)	0.159* (0.072)	0.471*** (0.045)
Conduct problems T1 ^a	-0.216** (0.084)	-0.177* (0.090)	-0.181** (0.068)	-0.296*** (0.089)	-0.502*** (0.066)	-0.178 (0.103)
Hyperactivity T1 ^a	-0.239*** (0.070)	-0.120 (0.089)	-0.310*** (0.069)	-0.344*** (0.086)	-0.318*** (0.090)	-0.480*** (0.071)
Peer problems T1 ^a	-0.064 (0.096)	-0.087 (0.081)	-0.202* (0.086)	-0.280*** (0.082)	-0.579*** (0.061)	-0.083 (0.096)
Emotional problems T1 ^a	-0.184 (0.095)	-0.216** (0.073)	-0.276*** (0.082)	-0.282*** (0.079)	-0.347*** (0.080)	-0.299*** (0.084)
Prosocial behaviour T1 ^a	0.159 (0.084)	0.032 (0.084)	0.097 (0.068)	0.311** (0.101)	0.446*** (0.069)	0.115 (0.109)
Conduct problems T2	-0.304*** (0.048)	-0.267*** (0.049)	-0.141* (0.055)	-0.432*** (0.040)	-0.520*** (0.037)	-0.173*** (0.048)
Hyperactivity T2	-0.301*** (0.049)	-0.328*** (0.050)	-0.341* (0.048)	-0.521*** (0.042)	-0.445*** (0.047)	-0.467*** (0.042)
Peer problems T2	-0.186*** (0.050)	-0.406*** (0.045)	-0.135* (0.051)	-0.298*** (0.045)	-0.748*** (0.021)	-0.229*** (0.045)
Emotional problems T2	-0.165** (0.056)	-0.272** (0.047)	-0.351*** (0.047)	-0.358*** (0.045)	-0.383*** (0.042)	-0.282*** (0.052)
Prosocial behaviour T2	0.290*** (0.050)	0.129* (0.055)	0.080 (0.050)	0.468*** (0.046)	0.548*** (0.038)	0.091 (0.073)

Note. Trait factors = true-score variable of the student self-reports (reference method); trait-specific method factors = method-specific deviations from the reference method for one trait, thus specific to teacher reports (non-reference method). S = student report, T = teacher report, EMO = emotional well-being, SOC = social inclusion, ASC = academic self-concept. Coding: Gender 0 = male, 1 = female. At-risk family context 0 = no (reference group), 1 = yes, psychosocial at-risk family context.

^a subsample of students with the same homeroom teacher at T1 and T2.

* $p < .05$.

** $p < .01$.

*** $p < .001$.

factors and not on the method factors of teacher reports; thus, Hypothesis 2b was not retained. Reading and mathematics achievement could explain the specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being (Hypothesis 2c). The predictive effect of reading achievement on the specificity in teacher reports of students' social inclusion was only very small, and the effect of mathematics achievement was not significant. A similar pattern emerged with regard to intelligence. Students' intelligence could explain the specificity in teacher reports for the three traits (Hypothesis 2d), with the highest effect size for academic self-concept.

As for behavioural skills assessed at T1, the four problem behaviour scales showed negative effects on trait-specific method factors (Hypothesis 2e), whereas prosocial behaviour showed positive effects (Hypothesis 2f). The effects were most pronounced for conduct problems and peer problems on the specificity in teacher reports of social inclusion, indicating that the higher a student's conduct and peer problems, the higher the teacher's ratings (compared to the student's self-reports) of all three aspects of subjective well-being. All effects on method factors were significant, with three exceptions: conduct problems, peer problems and prosocial behaviour had no significant effect on the specificity in teacher reports of students' academic self-concept.

At T2, the four problem behaviour scales showed negative effects (Hypothesis 2e), while the prosocial behaviour scale exhibited positive effects (Hypothesis 2f) on method factors (i.e., specificity of teacher

reports). Notably, for prosocial behaviour, no significant effect was found on either the trait factor or the trait-specific method factor of the academic self-concept. Compared to T1, all effects were more pronounced. Negative medium effect sizes were reported for conduct problems and peer problems on the specificity of teacher reports of social inclusion as well as for hyperactivity on the specificity of teacher reports of emotional well-being.

3.4. Teacher-student relationship as explanatory variable

As illustrated in Table 6, conflicts in the teacher-student relationship assessed at T1 were negatively associated with both the trait factors and trait-specific method factors. The most substantial effect was found for the specificity of teacher reports of social inclusion. Conversely, closeness showed only one significant effect, which was positive and again on the trait-specific method factor of social inclusion. The teacher-student relationship assessed at T2 could explain the specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being. The conflict scale exhibited small negative effects on all three trait factors, while very small positive effects were reported for the closeness scale. Focusing on the trait-specific method factors, the conflict scale revealed small negative effects on the academic self-concept and medium negative effects on emotional well-being and social inclusion (Hypothesis 3a). This indicates that the higher the teacher rated the teacher-student relationship

Table 6

Standardized regression coefficients and standard errors (in Parentheses) of the teacher-student relationship as explanatory variables on trait and method factors.

	Trait factors			Trait-specific method factors		
	EMO-S	SOC-S	ASC-S	EMO-T	SOC-T	ASC-T
T-S relationship, conflicts T1 ^a	-0.277*** (0.086)	-0.260*** (0.080)	-0.182** (0.077)	-0.304*** (0.085)	-0.531*** (0.065)	-0.220* (0.083)
T-S relationship, closeness T1 ^a	0.119 (0.088)	0.029 (0.108)	0.080 (0.071)	0.230 (0.119)	0.235* (0.094)	0.190 (0.111)
T-S relationship, conflicts T2	-0.302*** (0.048)	-0.232*** (0.059)	-0.140** (0.053)	-0.499*** (0.039)	-0.555*** (0.043)	-0.197*** (0.049)
T-S relationship, closeness T2	0.173** (0.053)	0.083 (0.054)	0.101* (0.051)	0.608*** (0.037)	0.462*** (0.043)	0.153** (0.055)

Note. Trait factors = true-score variable of the student self-reports (reference method); trait-specific method factors = method-specific deviations from the reference method for one trait, thus specific to teacher reports (non-reference method). S = student report, T = teacher report, EMO = emotional well-being, SOC = social inclusion, ASC = academic self-concept, T-S = teacher-student. Coding: Gender 0 = female, 1 = male.

^a subsample of students with the same homeroom teacher at T1 and T2.

* $p < .05$.

** $p < .01$.

*** $p < .001$.

as conflictual, the lower the teacher ratings – compared to self-reports – of students' emotional well-being and social inclusion. In contrast to T1, closeness in the teacher-student relationship (at T2) showed significant positive effects on the specificity of teacher reports (Hypothesis 3b). The effects of closeness on the specificity in teacher reports ranged from small to medium. For instance, the positive medium effect of closeness in the teacher-student relationship on emotional well-being indicated that the closer the student-teacher relationship was rated by the teacher, the higher the teacher rated a student's emotional well-being compared to self-reports.

4. Discussion

The present study examined teachers' judgment accuracy regarding three aspects of students' subjective well-being (i.e., emotional well-being, social inclusion, academic self-concept) in early primary education, and whether students' individual characteristics – particularly behavioural skills – and the teacher-student relationship could explain the (in)accuracy of teachers' judgments. We utilised data from 1583 students in Grade 3 and corresponding reports from their homeroom teachers, employing a CT-C(M-1) model to analyse the consistency between self-reports and teacher reports as well as the specificity of teacher reports. Explanatory variables were included as explanatory variables in the CT-C(M-1) model. Additionally, we accounted for longitudinal effects by including teacher ratings of selected individual characteristics and the teacher-student relationship assessed in Grade 1 for those students with the same homeroom teacher in Grade 1 and Grade 3.

As anticipated, the analyses revealed low consistencies between self-reports and teacher reports of students' emotional well-being and social inclusion (i.e., low judgment accuracy), alongside moderate consistencies for the academic self-concept. This implies that the specificity of the teacher reports was higher than the consistency for all three aspects of students' subjective well-being considered. Students' gender, academic achievement and intelligence were associated with the specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being, whereas an at-risk family context could not explain teacher judgment accuracy. Overall, behavioural problems were negatively associated with specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being, while prosocial behaviour was positively associated only with the two components emotional well-being and social inclusion. Students' behavioural skills assessed in Grade 1 could even predict the specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being in Grade 3. The teacher-student relationship could explain the specificity in teacher reports of students' subjective well-being, with positive associations for closeness and negative associations for conflicts. Regarding the teacher-student relationship assessed in Grade 1, only conflicts could predict the specificity in teacher reports.

4.1. On the challenges of judging students' subjective well-being

Not surprisingly, our findings regarding the first research question confirm previous research on teacher judgment accuracy regarding students' subjective well-being (e.g., [Urhahne & Zhu, 2015](#)). In contrast to most other corresponding studies, we focused on students in early primary school years and thus on younger students. This may indicate that younger students are not particularly 'good targets', to use [Funder's \(2012\)](#) terminology. One might also argue that children around the age of nine are less capable of evaluating their subjective well-being than older children, potentially resulting in larger discrepancies with teacher reports. Nevertheless, consistencies between the teacher reports and self-reports of Grade 3 students' subjective well-being were roughly the same as in other studies (e.g., [Venetz et al., 2019](#); [Zurbriggen et al., 2023](#)). This was also observed in the study by [Schwab et al. \(2020\)](#), which included a similar age group (Grade 4). Furthermore, our findings indicate that students tended to differentiate more between the three aspects of subjective well-being than teachers, and that teacher ratings can be generalised to some extent across the three aspects.

[Urhahne and Zhu \(2015\)](#) posited that one possible reason for the relatively low judgment accuracy is that teachers are less able to predict negative aspects of students' subjective well-being, as the majority of students report feeling well in school. This assumption is somewhat supported by our finding that teachers tended to underestimate the academic self-concept of students with higher emotional well-being. This is in line with [Venetz et al. \(2019\)](#), who found that higher emotional well-being and social inclusion were associated with smaller discrepancies between teacher ratings and students' self-reports of the two aspects, but not for the academic self-concept.

Previous studies have consistently shown higher teacher judgment accuracy for the academic self-concept than for other aspects of students' subjective well-being ([Urhahne & Wijnia, 2021](#)). One significant difference to other aspects is that the academic self-concept is closely linked to academic achievement, making it easier to assess by relying on school grades or achievement measures ([Helm et al., 2018](#)). It is important to highlight that the academic self-concept does not always count as an aspect of school-related subjective well-being, as is the case in the conception by [Hascher \(2012\)](#).

According to [Funder \(2012\)](#), availability and detection are two of the four key conditions under which accurate judgments are most likely to occur. Thus, the primary reason for the relatively low judgment accuracy of emotional well-being may be that it corresponds to an internal construct that is less available and consequently much more difficult for teachers to detect than more readily observable constructs. The first condition, as proposed by Funder's model, may be even more critical: relevance. Thus, the student must exhibit behaviour that is relevant to the trait, which can be inherently ambiguous. Beyond that, it is likely that teachers consider students' subjective well-being less relevant for learning and adaptive teaching than other characteristics such as

intelligence or academic achievement. Nevertheless, previous research supports the utility of subjective well-being for optimal development and academic success (Suldo et al., 2011). Therefore, the first step towards achieving better judgment accuracy may be to raise awareness about the relevance of students' school-related subjective well-being and the challenges of judging it from others' perspectives. This could also facilitate the implementation of the final condition in Funder (2012): the utilisation of the relevant behavioural information.

4.2. On behavioural cues and cognitive biases

Among the student characteristics considered in our study, students' behavioural skills had the most pronounced effects on teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being. Even behavioural skills assessed in Grade 1 showed small to medium effects on teacher judgment accuracy in Grade 3. The relatively strong associations may be explained by the fact that both measures were assessed via teacher reports. However, behavioural skills were also associated with students' self-reports of their subjective well-being, although generally less pronounced and not significant for some aspects. As expected, students' prosocial behaviour positively affected teacher judgments of students' subjective well-being, but not on academic self-concept. This latter finding is not self-evident, as empirical research has typically shown that prosocial behaviour is associated with academic achievement and positive educational outcomes (Collie et al., 2018). In contrast, hyperactivity negatively affected all three aspects of teacher judgments of students' subjective well-being. Overall, our findings regarding students' behaviour are in accordance with Funder's realistic accuracy model (Funder, 2012) and support the assumption that teachers rely on behavioural cues for their judgments – at least to a certain degree (Kenny & West, 2010).

Nonetheless, teacher reports of students' subjective well-being were also affected by less observable constructs. Students' academic achievement in Grade 1 not only predicted teacher judgment accuracy of students' academic self-concept but also of emotional well-being in Grade 3. Similar effects were noted for students' intelligence. Particularly the significant effects of intelligence on teacher judgments of students' emotional well-being suggest that a cognitive bias may be present when a teacher makes a judgment about a student's well-being. One such possible cognitive bias influencing teachers' judgments could be the well-known halo effect (Thorndike, 1920), which corresponds to a pervasive error where one characteristic of a person outshines – or overshadows, in the case of a reverse halo effect – other characteristics when making judgments (Forgas & Laham, 2022). In terms of teacher judgment accuracy, this means that a positive impression that a teacher has formed of a student may subsequently and predominantly, albeit unconsciously, alter the teacher's assessment of other characteristics of that student (Kaiser et al., 2013).

Similar mechanisms could be responsible for the small gender bias found in our study. Teachers tended to estimate girls' emotional well-being and social inclusion higher than that of boys (compared to self-reports). In contrast to previous studies (Schwab et al., 2020; Venetz et al., 2019), the academic self-concept was not affected by such a bias. Whether this is due to a heightened awareness of gender biases remains a matter of speculation. Nonetheless, accurately assessing a student's academic self-concept enables teachers to better tailor their teaching to their students' motivational needs, thereby creating a learning environment that is favourable for each student (Helm et al., 2018).

Contrary to our assumption, an at-risk family context did not affect teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being. Given the small sample size of students from an at-risk family context, low power seems a distinct possibility. It should also be noted that the family's level of psychosocial risk was assessed around the child's birth. Thus, the family's situation could have changed by the beginning of primary education, or the teachers may not have been aware of an at-risk situation. Another possible reason could be that teachers had no

stereotypical expectations about the students' family situation, or if they did, they suppressed such expectations in their judgments (Glock & Krolak-Schwerdt, 2014). An interesting secondary finding is worth noting: students from at-risk family contexts reported slightly lower subjective well-being, although the effect was small.

4.3. On the relevance of a positive teacher-student relationship and teacher attunement

A positive, low-conflict teacher-student relationship is considered to have beneficial functions for a student's learning and well-being (Bakchich et al., 2023; Koomen & Jellesma, 2015; Saxer et al., 2024). Our findings indicate that a conflictual teacher-student relationship negatively affects students' (self-rated) subjective well-being. Most notably, conflicts affected the teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being. The effect was most pronounced for students' social inclusion, but teachers' judgments of emotional well-being and academic self-concept were also biased. This unfavourable effect appeared to persist over the first three primary school years. Closeness in a teacher-student relationship, in contrast, positively affected teacher judgments of students' subjective well-being, albeit apparently to a lesser extent. This suggests that a close teacher-student relationship may come at the cost of overestimating a student's subjective well-being, potentially leading to a failure to detect, for instance, if a student does not feel comfortable at school.

Teachers' sensitivity and responsiveness to children's needs are crucial for younger students, particularly due to their lower capacity for self-regulation (Verschuere & Koomen, 2012). Since a caregiver's sensitivity towards a child's needs is a significant determinant of a high-quality child-caregiver relationship (Buyse et al., 2011), the role of the teacher as an attachment figure is likely to be particularly important in early school years (Verschuere & Koomen, 2012). By consistently providing secure, relatedness-supportive behaviours, teachers can create a school environment that nurtures students' basic psychological needs, which in turn promotes their subjective well-being (Conesa et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2014). In terms of students' social inclusion, teacher attunement is essential for implementing teaching activities and strategies that foster beneficial peer relationships in the classroom (Endedijk et al., 2022; Hoffman et al., 2015), thus enabling teachers to enact their 'invisible hand' (Farmer et al., 2011).

Teacher attunement is not only important regarding social aspects but also in addressing individual differences in other aspects of subjective well-being, making it crucial for the successful implementation of inclusive education. To enhance teacher judgment accuracy, several possibilities have been proposed (Zhu & Urhahne, 2021). To advance research on teacher judgment accuracy on students' subjective well-being, it could be beneficial to apply the conceptual model of teachers' assessment competence (Herppich et al., 2018; Südkamp & Praetorius, 2017) and to focus on judgment processes in different assessment situations relevant to students' subjective well-being in school.

4.4. Limitations and directions for future research

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, our study was based on data that was not explicitly designed to investigate teachers' judgment accuracy. Among others, students' subjective well-being of Grade 1 students had not been collected. A corresponding (primary) study design could have utilised the adapted PIQ version, which has been specifically designed for early learners (Grüter et al., 2023). Second, the sample of this study was collected in the German-speaking region of Switzerland, limiting the generalizability of our findings. Like many European countries, Switzerland has a predominantly individualistic culture. A recent study found that teachers' educational goals tend to reflect broader cultural norms, emphasising on self-direction, universalism, and benevolence (Oeschger et al., 2024). These values may shape how teachers perceive and assess students' well-being.

Third, we adopted a multi-dimensional framework of school-related subjective well-being and focused on three specific aspects. Future studies may consider other aspects of students' subjective well-being, such as physical complaints (Hascher, 2012), or may examine whether negative aspects are more easily detected than positive ones (Urhahne & Zhu, 2015). Fourth, social inclusion was assessed via self-reports, as students' subjective well-being was the focal point of our study. In light of the relatively high associations of students' behavioural skills with teacher ratings of students' social inclusion and considering previous research (Harks & Hannover, 2017; Schoop-Kasteler & Müller, 2021), it would be worthwhile to account for the perspectives of peers in the classroom (e.g., peer nominations). Fifth, the teacher-student relationship was assessed from the teachers' perspective. Accordingly, further investigations may include students' perspectives and account for student-teacher agreement regarding their relationship.

Sixth, we entered the explanatory variables as manifest variables in the CT-C(M-1) models to avoid further increasing the complexity of the models. To enhance the rigor of the analysis, a residual latent moderated structural equation approach with latent interaction effects could be applied (Koch, Kelava, & Eid, 2018). Finally, teachers' judgment accuracy over time was not analysed. Future studies could benefit from considering the temporal stability of teacher judgment accuracy in intervention studies (Zhu & Urhahne, 2021) or from including classroom-level factors (Karing et al., 2024), such as the social classroom climate and instructional quality.

5. Conclusion

Despite some limitations, this study extends previous research on teachers' judgment accuracy of students' subjective well-being by investigating whether students' individual characteristics and the teacher-student relationship can explain the low to moderate accuracy between teachers' ratings and students' self-reports of their subjective well-being in early primary education. Our findings indicate that teacher judgments are affected not only by students' gender, academic achievement and intelligence but also, more importantly, by students' behavioural skills. These effects appeared to persist over the first three primary school years. Based on our findings and theoretical considerations, it can cautiously be concluded that when the visibility of a construct to be judged is limited, teachers tend to rely on behavioural cues they possibly associate with the construct. Furthermore, the quality and duration of the teacher-student relationship, specifically closeness and conflicts, could explain and predict teachers' judgment accuracy. Overall, our findings point to a nuanced role of student behaviours and teacher-student relationships in shaping teachers' judgments of students' subjective well-being.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Carmen L.A. Zurbriggen: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Susanne Schwab:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Isabelle Kalkusch:** Resources, Data curation. **Alex Neuhauser:** Project administration, Resources, Investigation. **Andrea Lanfranchi:** Funding acquisition. **Peter Klaver:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2025.102754>.

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